

GLUCOCORTICOIDS INDUCED OSTEOPOROSIS: A MEDICINE INDUCED DISEASE

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Abstract. Diseases such as cancer, inflammation, respiratory, and autoimmune diseases are treated or managed using glucocorticoids (GCs), but this GC therapy has a significant side effect, which is the induction of osteoporosis, also termed glucocorticoids-induced osteoporosis (GIOP). The GIOP leads to an increase in bone absorption through decreasing the level of osteoblasts (bone-forming cells) and increasing the level of osteoclasts (bone-deleting cells), which leads to suppression of bone formation.

Keywords: glucocorticoids (GC), Osteoblast, Osteoclast, Osteoporosis, Bone.

Introduction to Osteoporosis

Administering the GCs in low dose for over a period of 3 months will lead to induction of osteoporosis, and the risk of osteoporosis is directly proportional to the duration and dosage of the GC being administered. The factors that influence the GIOP are age, sex, previous fractures, and other diseases. GIOP can be managed and treated if detected early through pharmacological interventions and non-pharmacological interventions such as exercises and food [1]

The most common metabolic disorder, which is currently affecting approximately around 200 million people worldwide, is osteoporosis, which remains underdiagnosed and untreated only to be identified when bone fracture occurs or a reduction in the bone mineral density is shown up in the blood test. Postmenopausal women and the elderly age group are most prevalent to this disease. The fracture-prone area of the body affected by osteoporosis includes the hip, wrist, and vertebral column [2].

Causes of Osteoporosis:

Imbalance between the osteoblast cell and the osteoclast cell plays a key role in the process of this diseases with chronic glucocorticoid therapy are prone to fractures of the femoral neck of the hip and vertebrae. As the GC therapy is started, there is a rapid bone loss (3-5%) followed by a steady phase (0.5-1%) each year. Prednisolone (2.5-7.5 mg daily), which is a low dose, can also be a factor in fracture risk if the dose is surged [3]

Drugs which cause osteoporosis

Cancer medicines

Thiazolidinediones

Proton pump inhibitors

Antiepileptics medicines

Glucocorticoids

Introduction to Glucocorticoids

The steroid hormones glucocorticoids (GCs) are commonly used to treat cancer, autoimmune diseases, and inflammation. To demonstrate its therapeutic and wide physiological effects, GCs bind to the GC receptor (GR) [4]. The GR is a member of the nuclear receptor superfamily of ligand-inducible transcription factors, which regulate a variety of physiological activities like as development, metabolism, and reproduction through gene transcription. The unliganded GR is mostly found in the cytoplasm, but it effectively and swiftly translocates to the nucleus upon hormone binding [5].

Mechanism of GIOP:

Gc leads to decreased calcium absorption in the stomach, increasing osteoclastogenesis and promoting the death of osteoblasts and osteocytes. The decrease in these cells leads to the reduction in bone formation and an increase in bone resorption, contributing to osteoporosis [6].

The effect of excess glucocorticoids on the formation and function of osteoblast, decreased osteogenic cell fate of stromal progenitor cells, suppressed proliferation of osteoprogenitors.

Some glucocorticoids drugs are beclomethasone, betamethasone, budesonide, cortisone, dexamethasone and many more [7].

Treatment of GIOP:

Treating and managing GIOP involves both non-pharmacological and pharmacological interventions, Bisphosphonates are used to prevent bone resorption, while calcium and vitamin D supplements are essential for maintaining bone health. Other treatments include calcitonin, denosumab, and teriparatide. Lifestyle modifications, such as a diet rich in calcium and vitamin D, regular weight-bearing exercise, and smoking cessation, are also recommended to prevent and manage GIOP [8].

Emerging therapies and investigational agents targeting bone resorption are lasofoxifene and cathepsin K inhibitors, and emerging and investigational agents targeting bone formation are donepezil and anti-sclerostin antibodies [9].

Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis is a serious side effect of long-term GC therapy. Early intervention, including risk assessment and appropriate treatment, is crucial in preventing fractures and managing osteoporosis in patients undergoing GC therapy [10].

Factors leading to osteoporosis

Gc drug, and the disease they are used

Beclomethasone [11]

Allergic Rhinitis

COPD

Asthma
Nasal polyps
Betamethasone [12]
Skin conditions
Rheumatic and Autoimmune disorders
Respiratory conditions
Fetal Lung Maturation
Budesonide [13]
COPD
Inflammatory bowel disease
Eosinophilic Esophagitis
Cortisone [14]
Arthritis
Tendinitis and bursitis
Allergic Reactions
Dexamethasone [15]
Autoimmune Disease
Allergic reactions and anaphylaxis
Inflammatory bowel disease

Conclusion: Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis is a serious side effect of long-term GC therapy. Early intervention, including risk assessment and appropriate treatment, is crucial in preventing fractures and managing osteoporosis in patients undergoing GC therapy.

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